

Psammobates tentorius tentorius
Karoo tent tortoise

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

© Zhongning Zhao

Group: Reptile

Size: maximum 15 cm for female, 10.5 cm for male

Distribution:

The Karoo tent tortoise occurs only in the lower and central Karoo region, between Touws River and Makhanda.

Importance:

The Karoo tent tortoise is an important seed disperser for various plant species and endemic to South Africa. It is arguably one of the most taxonomically confusing and morphologically polymorphic species of Testudines. It is listed as "Near Threatened" by the IUCN and is confined to the central and lower Karoo regions. Remarkably, no genomic studies have been conducted on any tortoise species in Africa or across the entire Southern Hemisphere.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 107.98 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 10.35 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Genome Length: 2.24 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.6% [Single: 97.3%, Duplicated: 2.4%]

Assembly N50: 3 436.17 kilobases

Contig number: 7201

Sample Contributor contact details:

Dr Zhongning Zhao

University of the Free State

orochi19851020@yahoo.com

DIPL**MICS**
CONNECTING RESEARCHERS & WORLD CLASS OMICS FACILITIES

Date Published 2025-07-17:

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16355357